

EXPERIMENTAL AND THEORETICAL STUDY OF DYNAMIC STOCHASTICITY EFFECTS UNDER CRACK PROPAGATION IN STRUCTURES

O.B. Naimark*, V.A. Barannikov, S.V. Uvarov, D.N. Naldae

*Institute of Continuous Media Mechanics
Ural Department of Russian Academy of Sciences
1 Ak. Korolev Street, 614061 Perm, Russia;
* and invited Professor at LAMEF-ENSAM*

SUMMARY: A theoretical and experimental study of crack propagation dynamics in PMMA is presented. The transition from a steady-state regime to a branching one and the stochastic scenario of crack propagation are investigated experimentally by considering fracture surface patterns and by high speed camera recording. We find that the mechanism for the change of the crack propagation regime is linked with the nonlinear dynamics of the microcracks ensemble at the crack tip and the formation of daughter cracks.

KEYWORDS: damage, crack, structures, localization.

INTRODUCTION

There is an upsurge of interest in the problem of crack advance through locally heterogeneous materials since a complete understanding could be a key to tough materials design. As a matter of fact, microstructural elements as grain boundaries, second phase precipitation, dislocation pile-ups, microcracks are able not only to force crack deflection by modifying locally the stress intensity factor, but also to change qualitatively the mechanisms of crack dynamics due to the interaction of the main crack with ensemble of the microscopic defects. As the consequence, the progress in the understanding has been made in the development of statistical physics of the defects ensemble, in the derivation of the corresponding continuum description and in the improving of the adequate experimental technique.

Experimental study, statistical and nonlinear continuum description of the microcrack ensemble evolution allowed us to establish specific properties of the system "solid with defects" and to study the scaling laws of the transition from damage to fracture [1]. It was found that failure scaling is the consequence of collective effects in the defects (microcracks) ensemble and is caused by universal laws of considered nonlinear system. The structure evolution is accompanied by non-equilibrium kinetic transitions that lead to the generation of localized modes of failure and sharp changes of the symmetry properties (topological transitions).

Nonlinear dynamics of crack propagation is the subject of the growing interest during last decade due to the experimental observation of the dynamic stochasticity effects and the nonlinearity (attractor) types of the equations developed in the framework of the statistical approach. The results of statistical analysis allow us to study the following phenomena:

- crack formation caused by generation of collective modes, which develop as instabilities with the blow-up kinetics in the defect ensemble localized on the spectrum of spatial scales;
- fractality and damage localization in the case of quasi-brittle fracture;
- propagation of fast crack in the brittle material.

Statistical Model and Constitutive Equations

In [1,2], the macroscopic tensor p_{jk} of microcrack density was introduced to characterize the volume concentration and the preferential orientation of microcracks. Constitutive equations were obtained due to the solution of the statistical problem and by the averaging microscopic tensor $s_{jk} = s \nu_{jk}$. This statistical description allow us to determine the characteristic solid responses caused by defects. The regimes are defined by two internal scales: characteristic scale of structural heterogeneity l_y and correlation radius l_c of interaction between defect. Three responses of material to the defect growth were established: monotonous ($\delta > \delta_*$), metastable ($\delta_c < \delta < \delta_*$) and unstable ($\delta < \delta_c$); δ_* and δ_c being the bifurcation points correspond to the change of the asymptotes.

Fig. 1: Nonlinear solid responses on microcrack growth

The monotonous response is characteristic of a weak interaction between defects. In metastable area the jump-like change of p_{jk} corresponds to the orientation ordering of the mesodefekt ensemble. The passes over the asymptotics can be recognized as topological transitions that lead to the symmetry changes due to the new organization in the defect system. Kinetic description of the defect growth and relation between damage and irreversible deformation are based on the assumption that the free energy F is determined by the statistical model. The free energy F reflecting the spectrum of the solid responses on the defect growth (Fig. 1) can be represented as the expansion

$$F = \frac{1}{2} A (\delta) p_{jk}^2 + \frac{1}{4} B p_{jk}^4 + \frac{1}{6} C (\delta) p_{jk}^6 + D \sigma_{jk} p_{jk} + \frac{1}{2} \chi (\nabla p_{jk})^2 \quad (1)$$

where A, B, C and D are the parameters of the expansion. Taking in view the polar character of the defect interaction the gradient term was introduced [3] that allowed us to describe the nonlocality effect in a “long-wave approximation”, χ is the nonlocality coefficient. The forms of the coefficients upon the quadratic term and the higher term provide a qualitative changes of material responses on the defect growth in bifurcation points δ_* and δ_c .

Thermodynamics of solid with these types of defects was developed in [1,2]. As it was established in [1] the quasi-brittle failure is characterized by the change of the mean size of the microcracks for the practically constant value of the concentration. Taking in view that the driving force of the microcrack growth kinetics is the free energy release, we obtain as the consequence of the evolution inequality (Ginsburg-Landau approach [4]) $\frac{\delta F}{\delta T} = \frac{\delta F}{\delta P_{\mathbb{k}}} \dot{P}_{\mathbb{k}} \leq 0$ ($\frac{\delta}{\delta P_{\mathbb{k}}}$ is the variation derivative) the kinetic equation for the microcrack density tensor $P_{\mathbb{k}}$

$$\frac{d P_{\mathbb{k}}}{d t} = -\Gamma \frac{\partial F}{\partial P_{\mathbb{k}}} + \frac{\partial}{\partial x_1} \left(\zeta \frac{\partial P_{\mathbb{k}}}{\partial x_1} \right), \quad (2)$$

where Γ is the kinetic coefficient, $\zeta = \Gamma \chi$. Using the potential $\Phi = F - \sigma_{\mathbb{k}} \varepsilon_{\mathbb{k}}$ for that the independent variables are $\sigma_{\mathbb{k}}$ and $P_{\mathbb{k}}$, and the determination of deformation tensor [2] $\varepsilon_{\mathbb{k}} = -\frac{\partial \Phi}{\partial \sigma_{\mathbb{k}}}$ we obtain the equation for the total deformation

$$\varepsilon_{\mathbb{k}} = \frac{1}{2\mu} \sigma'_{\mathbb{k}} + \frac{1}{2k} \sigma_{II} \delta_{\mathbb{k}} + D P_{\mathbb{k}}. \quad (3)$$

Eqn 2 and Eqn 3 represent the system of the constitutive equations of quasi-brittle solid with microcracks.

Let us consider the specific features of nonlinear system for $\delta \leq \delta_c$ passing the instability threshold P_c (Fig. 1). In this case the p -growth is governed by the difference in the orders of higher terms of expansion for free energy Eqn 1. Assuming the power law for the nonlocality parameter $\zeta = \zeta_0 (P_c) \hat{P}^\beta$ the kinetic equation for P can be written in the form [9]

$$\frac{\partial P}{\partial t} \approx S(P_c) \hat{P}^\omega + \frac{\partial}{\partial x} \left(\zeta_0 (P_c) \hat{P}^\beta \frac{\partial P}{\partial x} \right) \quad (4)$$

where $\hat{P} = P/P_c$ (in the following the "hat" is dropped), $\omega = 5/3$. It was shown in [3] that the self-similar solution for $t \rightarrow t_c$ exists and can be represented in the form

$$P_A = g(t) f(\xi), \quad \xi = \frac{x}{\phi(t)} \quad (5)$$

with the singular type of the time dependence $g(t) = G(1 - t/t_c)^{-m}$, where $g(t)$ governs the growth law of over the spectrum of the scales ζ_i (the eigenvalue spectrum); ϕ defines the half-width evolution of the localization area; $G > 0$ and $m > 0$ are the parameters of Eqn 1.

Fractality and damage localization

Fractals are the concern of a new geometry, whose primary object is to describe the great variety of natural structures that are irregular, rough or fragmented, having irregularities of various sizes that bear a special "scaling" relationship to one another. It was in 1984 that, for the first time, Mandelbrot et al [5] characterized the fractal nature of fracture surfaces of a steel. After their pioneering work other materials - mainly steels and ceramics - were examined by the same experimental method. Many experiments for all sorts of materials, both

brittle and ductile, analyzed using various experimental techniques demonstrate the universal value of the roughness exponent 0.8 [6]. Simultaneous using a standard scanning electron microscope and an atomic force microscope shows (for aluminum alloys and glass) [7,8,9] that roughness index of the small-length-scales regime is indeed close to 0.5. The experiments [10] carried out on concrete specimens also confirm the fact that the fractal characteristic is not a universal constant depending on the scaling domain where it is observed.

There has been a recent upsurge of activity in the statistical modeling of the crack formation and propagation. Two types of "fractal crack models" should be noted. These are:

- the crack grows on the initial defect due to the formation of the failure region in the vicinity of the crack tip [11] or due to the lattice fracture [12,13,14,15], which only illustrates the evolution of the main crack without taking into consideration the development of damage throughout the material ;
- the percolation model of fracture cluster growth [8].

The last includes:

- damage accumulation in the bulk of the specimen;
- generation and growth of the "fractured" clusters;
- formation of the percolation cluster which consists of the initial defect joined to adjacent clusters and defects.

From our point of view the percolation model is capable to more adequately describe the quasi-brittle fracture features. The modeling technique involving the solution of nonlinear kinetic equation of damage accumulation allows us to describe the crack localization and branching.

The nonhomogeneous materials with multiple interacting microcracks are dissipative systems, whose behaviour changes from regular to random at small variations of certain parameters. This phenomenon is caused by local instabilities of $p_{\mathbf{k}}$ beyond the thermodynamic branch of $p(\sigma)$ for $\delta < \delta_c$ (Fig. 1). Local instabilities in ensemble of defects are accompanied by alteration of the topological properties of the system. The regularities of the transition from damage to fracture were investigated for the prediction of the carbon-carbon composite strength [16,17]. The tests on plate specimens were carried out for uni-axial quasi-static loading in Y- direction (Fig. 4). The appropriate approximation of the kinetic equation in term of the p_{YY} - component was taken in the form (it provides the unstable response Fig. 1)

$$\dot{p}_{YY} = -\frac{1}{\tau_p} \left(p_{YY} - \left(\frac{\sigma_{YY}}{r_c} \exp(\beta p_{YY}) \right)^\alpha \right), \quad (6)$$

where "Y" is the direction parallel to the direction of applied stress, r_c is a characteristic strength of the elements (finite elements approximation), β is the parameter controlling the effective stress growth under damage accumulation and, α is the Weibull modulus. Parameters (α, β, r_c) were determined from the results of statistical analysis of tensile test measurements (constant rate of the clamps) on carbon-carbon composite specimens [16,17]. Experiments demonstrate characteristic features of deformation and fracture: the presence of microcracks in the bulk of the specimen; the influence of microcracking on the deformation behaviour of materials; fragmentation of the specimen across the regions subject to damage and highly statistical scattering of the specimen strength. For the case of uni-axial tension only the component p_{YY} of the tensor $p_{\mathbf{k}}$ is sufficient to characterize the microcrack accumulation

process. The problem of quasi-brittle fracture has been solved numerically [16,17] by the finite element method based on the equilibrium equation

$$\partial \sigma_{*k} / \partial x_k = 0 \quad (k=1,2), \quad (7)$$

the constitutive equation of elastic medium with microcracks (Eqn 3), the kinetic equation of damage accumulation (Eqn 6), boundary condition and the initial conditions. The choice of the boundary and initial conditions depends on the type of experiments simulated. Simulation of the deformation and fracture processes starts with modeling the heterogeneous material properties. We examined several variants:

- random distribution of the elasticity modulus;
- random initial condition for parameter P_{YY} ;
- random assignment of the kinetic equation constants (the strength r_s and Weibull modulus α) to each element of the finite element approximation.

The numerical results show that the last case is more attractive for modeling the localization process.

Fig. 2: Typical form of the percolation cluster

The algorithm of the "computer" fracture is following. At every step of the time we calculate a new value of the elastic modulus taking into account damage accumulation, and solve the elasticity problem to define the value of parameter P_{YY} . The element is broken, when P_{YY} reaches the critical value P_c ($P_c = 3 \cdot 10^{-4}$ is an experimental estimate). The macroscopic fracture corresponds to the formation of a percolation cluster that consists of fractured elements. The final step of fracture simulation is the fractal analysis of the percolation cluster. The cluster appears to be fractal in nature and with an increase of linear dimension L of the damaged array [6] its mass M (the number of failed elements) increases on the average as:

$$M(L) = AL^D, \quad (8)$$

where D is the fractal dimension, A is the effective amplitude. The mean value of A is obtained by averaging over the manifold realization of the percolation cluster. Fig. 5 compares two typical form of the percolation cluster. The process of kinetics and the topology of the cluster results from several reasons: (i) form of Eqn 6, (ii) value of the constant in Eqn 6 and Eqn 7, (iii) loading conditions, (iv) presence and size of the initial macrodefect. The combination of the above conditions may lead to the formation of the branched cluster (Fig. 2a) either slowly branched (Fig. 2b).

Fig. 3: Topological characteristics (fractal dimensions) of the damage cluster growth.

This approach was used to simulate failure development in specimens with an initial macroscopic defect located in the center (the macrocrack is normal to the tension direction) with characteristic size N_a (Fig. 3). The dependence $M(L)$ consists of two linear parts with the slopes determined by the fractal dimension D . Simulation of damage has demonstrated that under loading the initial stage is accompanied by preferential failure of elements located in the vicinity of the macroscopic defect ($D = 1$). The percolation cluster across the specimen results from coalescence of the cluster originating from the initial macrodefect with clusters in its immediate neighbourhood ($D = 1.4 - 1.7$). This is indicative of the qualitative change in the topology of damage accumulation process and the fracture mechanism replacement. The fractal dimension $D = 1$ supports the validity of approaches of fracture mechanics only at the initial stage of crack evolution.

Fig. 4: Critical concentration of failed elements x_c on initial macrodefect size N_a

The results of statistical simulation for the time of complete formation of the main cluster are plotted in Fig. 4. This dependence involves two parts with two asymptotics x_c^n and x_c^d . The

hand-right part corresponds to the formation of the branched cluster with the fractal dimension $D = 1.4 - 1.7$. The transient region between these parts defines the critical size N_a^c of the initial defect, which specifies two qualitatively different mechanisms of fracture according to the size of initial defects. It means that the highest reliability of materials is reached when the size of initial defect is not larger than N_a^c . In this case, the material exhibits the maximum of "dissipative capacity" and the damage accumulation in the specimen is more homogeneous. We now turn to the value of the parameter α in Eqn 6 that drives the instability. Fig. 5 shows that the change of the nonlinearity degree of kinetic equation α leads to a change in the topology of the final percolation cluster. The system behaviour yields two asymptotics. The vertical asymptotics involves defect accumulation in the bulk of material and formation of the branched cluster with the fractal dimension $D \sim 1.6 - 1.8$ which corresponds to a low nonlinearity degree. The horizontal asymptotics corresponds to the case when the system behaviour is defined by stress concentration in the crack tip, the fractal dimension is $D \sim 1.4$ and the slightly branched percolation cluster spreads predominantly normal to the loading direction.

Fig. 5: Fractal dimension versus nonlinearity degree of kinetic equation

Statistical Simulation of Crack Propagation

The experimental observations which motivate an extension of our theoretical study are:

- that cracks in amorphous brittle materials (glass, PMMA) seldom travel faster than 60% of the Rayleigh wave speed [14], although according to continuum theory [18] this wave speed should be the limited velocity;
- that at about 40% of Rayleigh wave speed there is a sharp transition from a single propagating crack to an ensemble of cracks, when a single crack undergoes a local change in topology and sprouts micro-branches[22], an acceleration of the crack slows sharply, the crack velocity starts to oscillate, and the amplitude of these oscillations is an increasing function of the mean velocity [19];
- that the fast propagating cracks emit the high-frequency acoustic waves [20], and the fracture surface shows a periodic structure [8,9] correlated with velocity oscillations [19].

Numerical simulation of the dynamic behaviour of cracks are carried out based on the previous simulation technique and using the equilibrium equation (Eqn 7), the constitutive equation of elastic medium with microcracks (Eqn 3) and the kinetic equation of damage accumulation in the form

$$\dot{p}_{ij} = -L_p \left(A p_{ij} + B p_k p_{kj} + C p_k p_{kl} p_{lj} + D \sigma_{ij} \right) + \frac{\partial}{\partial x_l} \left(\omega p_{ij}^2 \frac{\partial}{\partial x_l} p_{ij} \right). \quad (9)$$

Phenomenological parameters L_p, A, B, C, D, ω are determined as the results of approximation of the typical defect density curves. The critical stress and defect density of PMMA are $15 \cdot 10^7$ Pa (σ_c), 0.01 (p_c), respectively [21] and can be written as

$$A = -\frac{\sigma_c}{p_c}, \quad B = \frac{\sigma_c}{p_c^2}, \quad C = \frac{\sigma_c}{p_c^3}, \quad \omega = 10 \cdot 10^{-2}. \quad (10)$$

The choice of the boundary and initial conditions is dictated by real experimental conditions [19,20]. Modeling deformation and fracture processes starts with random assignment of the kinetic coefficient L_p to each element of the finite element approximation (the number of elements is 5000). The Weibull distribution function is used to obtain the random value of kinetic coefficient L_p (the main value of kinetic coefficient is about 10^5)

$$f(x) = \alpha \lambda x^{\alpha-1} \exp(-\lambda x^\alpha). \quad (11)$$

Simulation results are in good qualitative agreement with the distinguishing crack evolution features observed experimentally.

Fig. 6: Crack length versus time (a), mean daughter crack length versus applied stress(b).

We obtain the jump-like crack moving, oscillations of the crack length and velocity (Fig. 6a). The boundary condition (uniform displacement of the horizontal specimen sides) provides the constant velocity of energy dissipation in the crack tip resulting in the uniform mean velocity of crack propagation (Fig. 6a).

The main goal of our numerical experiments is to simulate the single crack propagation - crack ensemble motion transition. We have calculated the mean length of daughter crack (the width of percolation cluster) depending on the applied stress. Each point on the curve is averaged over 40 realizations (Fig.6b). Passing through the critical stress (at crack velocity about 40% of the Rayleigh wave speed) the mean daughter crack length increases (Fig. 6b), which fits fairly well experimental data [19]. Fig. 7 illustrates the characteristic spatial distribution of defect density for the stress level below critical stress - a single propagating crack (Fig.7a) and above it - a branching crack (Fig.7b).

Fig. 7: Spatial-time distribution of defect density for different stress levels.

CONCLUSION

1. The transition from damage to fracture is realised under the nucleation of the damage localized zones with blow-up defect growth kinetics (peak-regime kinetics).
2. The nature of stochastic behaviour of quasi-brittle materials is the dynamic stochasticity caused by the nonlinear properties of the defect ensemble. The experimentally observed regimes of crack propagation (steady-state and branching) are the consequences of the rate of the free energy release or the non-linearity power of the microcrack density kinetic equation.
3. One of motivations of this work was the comparison between the experimental results on the fracture heterogeneous materials and model of percolation cluster growth. This model is certainly an over-simplification of reality, furthermore it shows that at least on a qualitative level percolation based on nonlinear kinetics could be a good model for crack propagation.
4. The topological invariants of transition from damage to fracture are established as the inherent property of a nonlinear system "solid with microcrack". The variation in fractal dimension correlates with fracture mechanism replacement.

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